

Detection of Brain Disorder and Applicability of Machine Learning

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Abstract

With the growth in the brain disorder diseases caused by brain tumours, the need for early detection of the diseases are increasing. The primary problem with the early detection method is the higher dependency on the preliminary diagnosis of the MR image data. The collection process of the MR images is always challenging due to the fact that the images are captured from magnetic sources and magnetic sources are always prone to the addition noises along with added outliers and missing values for detailed analysis. Once the MR images are collected, further regions in the MR images must be classified in terms of normal and anomalous cells. This classification builds the foundation for growth analysis and further the prediction of the diseases. During the classification process, the complexity of the models is expected to reach higher time complexity and result into delay in detection. Further, the early detection processes are built on the machine learning models, which are again having a strong demand for cleaned and pre-processed data. Hence, the early disease detection is always been a challenge for researchers. Nevertheless, many parallel research attempts can be seen, which aim to solve such problems. In this study the issues related to these three primary steps for early disease detection caused by the human brain tumours are analysed and further the problems are realized using the mathematical modelling methods for better understanding. This study also lists the primary concerns with all parallel research outcomes and recommends a guideline for solving those research problems for making the world of early disease detection and prediction a must better place.

Keywords— Brain Tumour, Class Detection, parametric extraction, MR Image, MRI Segmentation, Early Disease Predictions

I. INTRODUCTION

The generalized structure of the human body based on physiological aspects identifies the human brain as the central component of the nervous systems. The complete control of the human body, including the other sensory organs are controlled by the human brain and in order to accommodate the complex neuron structure, the human brain, in the adult phases weighted between 1.3 to 1.4 Kgs. The composition of the human brain is consisting of neurons, supporting the neurons, the soft tissues and to house the tissues, the glial cells. This understanding can be inferred from the recent brain imaging survey carried out by K. L. Bigos et al. [1] in the year 2016. Nevertheless, the complete analysis and the concrete understanding of the functionalities of the human brain is highly challenging due to the very intricated neuron structures. The attempts by the S. Herculano-Houzel et al. [2] have made significant progress in order to formulize the number of neurons and the connectivity pattern for information processing. Similar attempt by the report Brain Facts and Answers [3] reported in 2018 have also justified the work by S. Herculano-Houzel et al. [2] and made it widely accepted. Nonetheless, it is natural to realize that any defects in the brain tissues can cause serious physiological and phycological disorders in the human life. Thus, for many years multiple researchers have dedicated their studies in understanding and finding the protective measures for the brain tissues.

After a decade long research, the outcomes from the various researchers are confirming that the primary reason for the brain disfunction is caused by the presence of the tumorous cells in the human brain. The tumours cells can be demonstrate high growth rates over the year and some of the studies have showcased that the tumour cells, in the initial days does not signify a higher growth, however in the due course of time, the cell division pattern changes drastically and convert the nature of the tumour from benign to the malignant class. The research work carried out by L. M. De Angelis et al. [4] have confirmed that fact, the tumours growth in the brain cells may not be causing life threats but can cause permanent damage in the perseverance aspects. Thus, the study of the human brain and identification of the tumour type in the early stages can result in fastening the treatment and medication process.

In the recent time, with the availability of the sufficient data and sufficient computing capabilities automating the detection of the tumour cell growths and further identifying the potential threats on the human nervous systems is highly possible and must be the need of the current research. Thus, this work aims to identify the outcomes of the parallel researches in order to recognize the research gaps in those research outcomes.

This work is organized as follows: The first section focuses on the fundamental understanding of human brain tissues. The second section introduces the various aspects of the classification of tumour cells. The third section explores the class detection outcomes. The fourth section explores the segmentation processes. Fifth section studies the mathematical models and their applications. Sixth section studies the outcomes of the research on early disease prediction. Seventh section explores the simulation results. The last section summarizes the recommendations.

II. FUNDAMENTALS OF HUMAN BRAIN TUMOURS TISSUES

In this section of the work, the fundamental understanding of the human brain tumour cell issues is discussed. This understanding will certainly help in realizing the strategies to be deployed for identification of the image processing and further the data extraction methods for human brain images. The primary composition of the malignant tumour cells is the glioma. The glioma is produced by the glial cells, which again are primarily responsible for human brain size developments. The study conducted by M. L. Goodenberger et al. [5] have showcased that the malignant tumours are generally caused by the glioma cells. This fundamental conclusion has made the advanced human brain imaging [Fig – 1] possible and the work of J. Meng et al. [6] is one such example. Such models have made the task of analysis of human brain functional units and also identification of functional disorders in the human brain possible.

Fig. 1 Anatomy of Human Brain

Furthermore, based on the rate of growth in human brain tumour cells, primarily the gliomas cells, the tumour cells can be further classified into four categories. The categorization is primarily done based on the various characteristics such as size, growth rate, radius, curvature and many others with the severity caused in terms of the brain functions. The report by WHO and again studies published by D. N. Louis et al. [7] have justified the categorization process based on the previously mentioned parameters from Grade – 1 to Grade – 4 [Fig – 2].

Fig. 2 Visual Differences of Tumour types

The initial two grades are less lethal in terms of disordering the brain functions and other connected diseases, where as the last two categories are identified as more lethal for damaging a greater part of the

human brain cells. The observation made by E. B. Claus et al. [8] and K. A. Jaeckle et al. [9] demonstrates that the conversion rate from the lower grades to the higher grade is possible and nearly sixty percent of the cases the conversion from lower grade to the higher grade is observed.

Thus, this study recommends that, during the analysis of the human brain tumour cells, the growth rate must be considered to analysing the change in severity for all cases. Further predicting the growth rate can reduce the risk of loss of life to a greater extend.

Nevertheless, the process recommended by the parallel researchers for identification and detection of the human brain tumours must incorporate the phases such as

- Correct identification of the human brain tumours classes
- Extraction of the brain tumour cell analysis parameters for Identification of the brain tumour severity
- Finally, prediction of the connected diseases caused by these tumour cells, which are present in certain part of human brain regions

Henceforth, the parallel research works from all these domains, demonstrating such outcomes, are analysed in the fourth coming sections of this study.

III. BRAIN TUMOUR CLASS DETECTION – SURVEY & COMPARISONS

In this section of the work, the parallel research outcomes from various research attempts on identification and detection of the tumour classes are discussed and analysed for identification of the gaps in the research.

Almost for a decade, the analysis of the human brain tumour and determining the class of the tumours are the focus of many researchers. A significant number of research attempts have reported various outcomes on the classification of the tumours based on severity and transformation into higher classes. Primarily, these researches are categorised into three major categories as showcased by E. Konukoglu et al. [10]. The categories of these types of researches are vivo, vitro and silico. However, the models utilized by these research attempts are based on the growth analysis of the tumour cells as summarized by Z. Wang et al. [11].

The notable outcome presented by the researcher T. Roose et al. [12] have clearly indicates that the growth patten must be the primary composition of the class detection analysis and the hybrid models for detection of the growth can generate better predictive models. Nevertheless, the analysis of the growth pattern can be high complex process and framework deployed for the same purpose can also be highly time complex. The work presented by R. P. Araujo et al. [13] have suggested a much simpler model for formulizing the growth patterns and further utilize the pattern for the prediction of tumour cell growths. Nonetheless, this existing model is highly dependent on the nature of the data and correctness of the data, thus the added pre-processing phases must be included during such model utilization. Hence, these models are criticised by other research attempts for higher complexity due to the practical reasons.

In the other hand, the hybrid models can be justified with the noise in the data or outliers in the data during the initial modelling and further during the predictive analysis. The models showcased in the works by C. S. Hoge et al. [14] and J. D. Humphrey et al. [15] utilizes the upvoting methods for combining the best results from various models, which are used to create the hybrid models.

Thus, regardless to mention that for the analysis of human brain tumours, this study recommends the hybrid models, where one model can be designed for pre-processing of the data.

Further, the comparative analysis of these research works is quantified here [Table – 1].

TABLE I
BRAIN TUMOUR CLASS DETECTION - COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

Frameworks		E. Konukoglu et al. [10]	Z. Wang et al. [11]	T. Roose et al. [12]	C. S. Hoge et al. [14]	J. D. Humphrey et al. [15]
Comparative Parameters	Segmentation Accuracy	Moderate	High	Moderate	Low	High
	Feature Extraction	Not Available	Not Available	Available	Not Available	Not Available
	Classification	Not Available	Available	Available	Not Available	Available
	Modelling	Available	Available	Available	Available	Available
	Complexity	High	High	Low	High	Moderate

Henceforth, in the next section of this study formulates the problem using mathematical models for better understanding.

IV. BRAIN TUMOUR CLASS DETECTION – PROBLEM FORMULATION

After the detailed understating of the parallel research work with identification of the problems in those research outcomes, in this section, this study presents the problem related to the human brain tumour class detection.

Lemma – I: A class detection method's accuracy is increased by reducing the missing or outlier values.

Proof: If the total dataset consists of all the observations made in a given period, then the D_i -value can be formulated by taking into account the n number of observations,

$$D[] = \sum_{i=1}^n D_i \quad (\text{Eq.1})$$

As the data collected at this point in time is mainly derived from the MR images, each and every observation or data point is a combination of various parameters such as the image contrast, pixel density, and the position of the objects,

$$D_i = \langle C, PD, OP \rangle \quad (\text{Eq.2})$$

Regardless to mention here, that the contract, pixel density or the object position is also a part of collection, which are extracted from the MR image data. Thus, for each of the parameter, for a total number of k instances, the following relation can be assumed,

$$C[] = \sum_{i=1}^k C_i \quad (\text{Eq.3})$$

$$PD[] = \sum_{i=1}^k PD_i \quad (\text{Eq.4})$$

And,

$$OP[] = \sum_{i=1}^k OP_i \quad (\text{Eq.5})$$

Nevertheless, the complete collection of the contract, pixel density or the object position is assumed to have some outliers or noise or missing values. Assuming that, a total of k_1 number of instances are correct and k_2 number of instances are bounded to have some anomalies, then this can be again formulated as,

$$C[] = \sum_{i=1}^{k_1} C_i + \sum_{j=1}^{k_2} C_j \quad (\text{Eq.6})$$

$$PD[] = \sum_{i=1}^{k_1} PD_i + \sum_{j=1}^{k_2} PD_j \quad (\text{Eq.7})$$

And,

$$OP[] = \sum_{i=1}^{k_1} OP_i + \sum_{j=1}^{k_2} OP_j \quad (\text{Eq.8})$$

Assuming that,

$$K = K_1 + K_2 \quad (\text{Eq.9})$$

Again, from the Eq. 1 and Eq. 2, the following can be re-written,

$$D1_i = \langle C_i, PD_i, OP_i \rangle \quad (\text{Eq.10})$$

$$D2_i = \langle C_j, PD_j, OP_j \rangle \quad (\text{Eq.11})$$

Finally,

$$D1[] = \sum_{i=1}^n D1_i \quad (\text{Eq.12})$$

And

$$D2[] = \sum_{i=1}^n D2_i \quad (\text{Eq.13})$$

Here, $D1[]$ with $D1_i$ and $D2[]$ with $D2_i$ are the datasets which are anomaly reduced and with anomaly respectively.

Further, assuming that ϕ is the algorithm for class detection for the brain tumours, then while applying the same algorithm for $D1[]$ and $D2[]$ shall produce two different accuracy measures as, λ_1 and λ_2 . These can be formulated as,

$$\lambda_1 = \phi(D1[]) \quad (\text{Eq.14})$$

And,

$$\lambda_2 = \phi(D2[]) \quad (\text{Eq.15})$$

Many parallel research attempts have proven that the reduction of the noises or outliers or the missing values can significantly improve the accuracy of classification algorithms, thus the following can be stated,

$$\lambda_1 \gg \lambda_2 \quad (\text{Eq.16})$$

Thus, the process with data cleaning measures will produce better classification of the tumour classes.

Further, in the next section of this work, the parametric analysis of the human brain tumour cells is discussed.

V. BRAIN TUMOUR PARAMETRIC ANALYSIS FOR SEVERITY – SURVEY & COMPARISONS

After Analysing the classification process for the human brain cell tumours on the existing researchers, in this section of the work, the parallel research outcomes on the parametric analysis and presided by the segmentation process is analysed.

The segmentation process is one of the fundamental processes for brain tumour detection on the MR images. The primary principle of the segmentation process is to separate the image regions based on a wide variety of parameters in order to identify the normal regions and the abnormal regions of the MR images. The normal regions of the MR image classify the normal brain tissues and the abnormal regions signifies the brain tissues which may cause multiple disorders. The work by Nilesh et al. [16] have presented the initial survey of the segmentation processes on the MR images.

In the parallel research outcomes, it is clearly observable that, various segmentation methods are deployed for classification of the image regions. The popular methods, such as K – Mean classification method, defines a wide range of parameters for deploying such method for image segmentations and further classifications. The notable work by Nameirakpam et al. [17] have presented the classification method using K – Means for MR image segmentation by deploying the parameters such as contract and median value extracted during the image filtration process. The primary advantage highlighted in this existing method is to deploy the clustering method as the outcome of the standard K – Means algorithm can report the final two classes are normal and abnormal regions of the MR images for quick post processing.

Yet another strategy deployed by Abubaker et al. [18] have demonstrated that, the use of hybrid algorithms for image segmentation instead of only using a standard customized algorithm can result in higher accuracy as the standard up-voting methods can rectify the outcomes from each method and finally provide the higher accuracy summarization. In this existing method, the first algorithm is designed to identify the nearest

neighbours and the second algorithm can fine tune the clusters based on the outcomes of the first algorithm. Regardless, to mention in the absence of the higher performing computing resources, the time complexity can be very high and due to this limitation, this work is criticized by many research attempts.

In the recent time, few of the parallel research attempts have showcased object-based identification and further classification of the image regions into classes. The work by Mohammadreza et al. [19] have showcases similar outcomes for identification of the image objects using the higher level of properties such as objects in the image. These methods are proven to be higher time efficient, but during the processing of the 3D image objects due to the violation of the image stability and overlapping images, these processes are again criticized.

The research for finding the best segmentation process for detection of brain tumours is not concluded and the work by Vishnuvarthanana et al. [20] and Cabria et al. [21] is the standard proof for that.

Further, the comparative analysis of these research works is quantified here [Table – 2].

TABLE II
BRAIN TUMOUR PARAMETRIC ANALYSIS FOR SEVERITY – COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

Methodology, Author & Year	MR Image Noise Removal	Image Segmentation Method Time Complexity	Image Segmentation Method Accuracy	Growth Rate Detection	Curvature Detection	Accuracy in region detection	Severity Analysis	Ranking (As Low as Better)
K -Means, Nameirakpam et al. [17], 2015	Yes	Low	80	No	No	Low	No	3
Improved K-Means, Mohamed Abubaker et al. [18], 2013	Yes	Low	79	No	No	Low	No	4
Random Tree, Mohammadreza Soltaninejad et al. [19], 2017	Yes	Moderate	72	No	No	Moderate	No	6
Unsupervised Learning, G. Vishnuvarthanana et al. [20], 2016	Yes	High	85	No	No	High	No	2
Fusion Methods, Iván Cabria et al. [21], 2017	Yes	High	78	No	No	Moderate	No	5

Henceforth, in the next section of this study formulates the problem using mathematical models for better understanding.

VI. BRAIN TUMOUR PARAMETRIC ANALYSIS FOR SEVERITY – PROBLEM FORMULATION

After the detailed understating of the parallel research work with identification of the problems in those research outcomes, in this section, this study presents the problem related to the human brain tumour parametric analysis.

Lemma – II: The parallel processing of the algorithms for parametric extraction and the segmentation can significantly reduce the time complexity.

Proof: Assuming that the total dataset, $D[]$, is the collection of individual data points, D_i , then this relation can be formulated for a total of n number of observations as,

$$D[] = \sum_{i=1}^n D_i \quad (\text{Eq.17})$$

As the accumulated data collected at this point in time is mainly derived from the MR images, each and every observation or data point is a combination of various parameters such as the image contrast, pixel density, and the position of the objects. Thus, this can be formulated as,

$$D_i = \langle C, PD, OP \rangle \quad (\text{Eq.18})$$

The object position, pixel density, and contract are part of the collection process that is derived from the images captured by the MR scanner. For each of these parameters, the following relationship can be assumed for a given number of instances,

$$C[] = \sum_{i=1}^k C_i \quad (\text{Eq.19})$$

$$PD[] = \sum_{i=1}^k PD_i \quad (\text{Eq.20})$$

And,

$$OP[] = \sum_{i=1}^k OP_i \quad (\text{Eq.21})$$

Further, assuming that, the algorithm, φ_1 , is deployed for extraction of the parameter values from dataset and the other algorithm, φ_2 , is deployed for the segmentation process, each algorithm must have separated time complexity for completing the processes, which are t_1 and t_2 respectively.

This can be formulated as,

$$t_1 \leftarrow \varphi_1(D[]) \quad (\text{Eq.22})$$

And,

$$t_2 \leftarrow \varphi_2(D[]) \quad (\text{Eq.23})$$

Henceforth, the total time consumed for running these algorithms in sequential and parallel, can be assumed as, T_1 and T_2 . These can be formulated as,

$$T_1 = (t_1 \cup t_2) - (t_1 \cap t_2) \quad (\text{Eq.24})$$

And,

$$T_2 = (t_1 \cup t_2) \quad (\text{Eq.25})$$

Regardless to mention, the time complexity for the parallel processing must be less than the time complexity of the sequential processing of both the algorithms.

$$T_1 \ll T_2 \quad (\text{Eq.26})$$

Henceforth, this work recommends the algorithms to be deployed for feature or parameter extraction and segmentation must be overlapped in order to achieve lower time complexity.

Further, in the next section of this work, the early disease detection of the human brain tumour cells is discussed

VII. DISEASE PREDICTION BY MACHINE LEARNING – SURVEY

After the detailed understanding of the existing methods for classification and segmentation methods, in this section of the work the disease prediction for early detection methods are analysed.

The major inputs for the disease detection and early predictions can be captured from the initial analysis of the MR images and relevant information generated from the previous two sections from this study.

The work by C. C. Benson et al. [22] have significantly highlighted the benefits of early detection of the tumour class for further analysis of the growths and prediction of the diseases. Nevertheless, the initial diagnosis from the MR images are highly crucial and the work showcased by Jenitta et al. [23] have make some significant guidelines regarding the initial diagnosis processes.

During the collection of information, in order to get higher accuracy of the prediction process, many of the parallel research outcomes have demonstrated higher ordered and much detailed collection of the data. Nonetheless, the work by Shakeel et al. [24] have criticised such research attempts for violation of the individual privacies during observations. This work has made the data collection process much critical related to historical information about the patients for building a higher accuracy model.

After the data collection process, ensuring the data is free from any noises or outlier or missing values is highly important for achieving the higher accuracy of the models. Many customized guidelines before applying any machine learning methods for tumour detection is listed in the work by Baskar et al. [25].

As most of the existing research outcomes are highly unique and cannot be quantified into a single metric, thus this study cannot be formulated into a specific metric for analysis.

VIII. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS RESULTS

In this section of the work, the parallel research outcomes are tested on the BRATs [26] dataset and the results are furnished here.

Firstly, the detection of the brain cell density is analysed for various parallel research attempts [Table – 3].

TABLE III
BRAIN CELL DENSITY ANALYSIS

Methodology, Author & Year	Test Run Sequence #	Brain Cell Size (micrometres) Detected	Brain Cell Size (micrometres) Actual	Deviation in Detection (%)
K -Means, Nameirakpam et al. [17], 2015	P1	33.5394	39.1024	16.59
K -Means, Nameirakpam et al. [17], 2016	P2	33.5394	35.7774	6.67
K -Means, Nameirakpam et al. [17], 2017	P3	64.1938	68.5868	6.84
K -Means, Nameirakpam et al. [17], 2018	P4	64.1938	67.1798	4.65
K -Means, Nameirakpam et al. [17], 2019	P5	62.9174	66.3024	5.38
Improved K-Means, Mohamed Abubaker et al. [18], 2013	P6	62.9174	67.3104	6.98
Improved K-Means, Mohamed Abubaker et al. [18], 2013	P7	63.1617	71.2127	12.75
Improved K-Means, Mohamed Abubaker et al. [18], 2013	P8	63.1617	67.7597	7.28
Improved K-Means, Mohamed Abubaker et al. [18], 2013	P9	61.5828	69.3468	12.61
Improved K-Means, Mohamed Abubaker et al. [18], 2013	P10	61.5828	65.2078	5.89
Random Tree, Mohammadreza Soltaninejad et al. [19], 2017	P11	33.5415	42.1145	25.56
Random Tree, Mohammadreza Soltaninejad et al. [19], 2017	P12	33.5415	39.1435	16.70
Random Tree, Mohammadreza Soltaninejad et al. [19], 2017	P13	33.6256	43.5506	29.52
Random Tree, Mohammadreza Soltaninejad et al. [19], 2017	P14	33.6256	41.7486	24.16

Soltaninejad et al. [19], 2017				
Random Tree, Mohammadreza Soltaninejad et al. [19], 2017	P15	33.6245	37.6885	12.09
Unsupervised Learning, G. Vishnuvarthanana et al. [20], 2016	P16	33.6245	42.2765	25.73
Unsupervised Learning, G. Vishnuvarthanana et al. [20], 2016	P17	32.7956	35.3486	7.78
Unsupervised Learning, G. Vishnuvarthanana et al. [20], 2016	P18	32.7956	40.3496	23.03
Unsupervised Learning, G. Vishnuvarthanana et al. [20], 2016	P19	32.7828	41.9478	27.96
Unsupervised Learning, G. Vishnuvarthanana et al. [20], 2016	P20	32.7828	37.3478	13.92
Fusion Methods, Iván Cabria et al. [21], 2017	P21	42.5384	49.8154	17.11
Fusion Methods, Iván Cabria et al. [21], 2017	P22	42.5384	45.1244	6.08
Fusion Methods, Iván Cabria et al. [21], 2017	P23	64.7527	69.0477	6.63
Fusion Methods, Iván Cabria et al. [21], 2017	P24	64.7527	70.2877	8.55
Fusion Methods, Iván Cabria et al. [21], 2017	P25	65.3569	72.3769	10.74

The size and location of the tumor depend on the accuracy of the brain cell count. This is why the accuracy of the brain cell count is so important.

The detection accuracy of the outcomes of parallel research programs has a significant variance. This is the reason why the mean deviation of these research methods is presented [Table – 4].

TABLE IV
BRAIN CELL DENSITY MEAN DEVIATION ANALYSIS

Methodology, Author & Year	Mean Deviation in Detection (%)
K -Means, Nameirakpam et al. [17], 2015	08.03
Improved K-Means, Mohamed Abubaker et al. [18], 2013	09.10
Random Tree, Mohammadreza Soltaninejad et al. [19], 2017	21.60
Unsupervised Learning, G. Vishnuvarthanana et al. [20], 2016	19.69
Fusion Methods, Iván Cabria et al. [21], 2017	09.82

Thus, the parallel research outcomes are bottlenecked with a higher deviation of inaccuracy for the detections. The results are also visualized graphically here [Fig – 3].

Fig. 3 Brain Cell Density Mean Deviation Analysis

Secondly, the detection of the brain cell tumour size is analysed for various parallel research attempts [Table – 5].

TABLE V
BRAIN CELL TUMOUR SIZE ANALYSIS

Methodology, Author & Year	Test Run Sequence #	Tumour Size (micrometres) Detected	Tumour Size (micrometres) Actual	Deviation in Detection (%)
K -Means, Nameirakpam et al. [17], 2015	P1	4.1238	4.7135	14.30
K -Means, Nameirakpam et al. [17], 2016	P2	4.1238	5.0686	22.91
K -Means, Nameirakpam et al. [17], 2017	P3	7.9156	8.5375	7.86

K -Means, Nameirakpam et al. [17], 2018	P4	7.9156	8.8144	11.35
K -Means, Nameirakpam et al. [17], 2019	P5	9.4525	9.7024	2.64
Improved K-Means, Mohamed Abubaker et al. [18], 2013	P6	9.4525	10.3322	9.31
Improved K-Means, Mohamed Abubaker et al. [18], 2013	P7	8.6357	9.0063	4.29
Improved K-Means, Mohamed Abubaker et al. [18], 2013	P8	8.6357	8.8496	2.48
Improved K-Means, Mohamed Abubaker et al. [18], 2013	P9	7.5182	8.2630	9.91
Improved K-Means, Mohamed Abubaker et al. [18], 2013	P10	7.5182	7.9381	5.59
Random Tree, Mohammadreza Soltaninejad et al. [19], 2017	P11	4.1069	4.3338	5.52
Random Tree, Mohammadreza Soltaninejad et al. [19], 2017	P12	4.1069	4.7218	14.97
Random Tree, Mohammadreza Soltaninejad et al. [19], 2017	P13	3.3498	3.7911	13.17
Random Tree, Mohammadreza Soltaninejad et al. [19], 2017	P14	3.3498	4.1909	25.11
Random Tree, Mohammadreza Soltaninejad et al. [19], 2017	P15	3.3602	4.1012	22.05
Unsupervised Learning, G. Vishnuvarthanana et al. [20], 2016	P16	3.3602	4.1237	22.72
Unsupervised Learning, G. Vishnuvarthanana et al. [20], 2016	P17	8.1456	8.8100	8.16
Unsupervised Learning, G. Vishnuvarthanana et al. [20], 2016	P18	8.1456	8.3360	2.34
Unsupervised Learning, G.	P19	8.1968	9.1157	11.21

Vishnuvarthanana et al. [20], 2016				
Unsupervised Learning, G. Vishnuvarthanana et al. [20], 2016	P20	8.1968	9.0365	10.24
Fusion Methods, Iván Cabria et al. [21], 2017	P21	7.7014	8.0571	4.62
Fusion Methods, Iván Cabria et al. [21], 2017	P22	7.7014	8.1079	5.28
Fusion Methods, Iván Cabria et al. [21], 2017	P23	9.6640	9.9717	3.18
Fusion Methods, Iván Cabria et al. [21], 2017	P24	9.6640	10.2064	5.61
Fusion Methods, Iván Cabria et al. [21], 2017	P25	7.0493	7.5272	6.78

Regardless to mention that, the detection of the tumour sizes highly depends on the actual brain cell size detection and the erroneous detection of the brain cell sizes will further lead to incorrect detection of the tumour sizes.

The mean deviation of these parallel research outcomes is analysed [Table – 6].

TABLE VI
BRAIN CELL TUMOUR SIZE MEAN DEVIATION ANALYSIS

Methodology, Author & Year	Mean Deviation in Detection (%)
K -Means, Nameirakpam et al. [17], 2015	11.81
Improved K-Means, Mohamed Abubaker et al. [18], 2013	06.31
Random Tree, Mohammadreza Soltaninejad et al. [19], 2017	16.17
Unsupervised Learning, G. Vishnuvarthanana et al. [20], 2016	10.93
Fusion Methods, Iván Cabria et al. [21], 2017	05.09

Thus, the parallel research outcomes are bottlenecked with a higher deviation of inaccuracy for the detections. The results are also visualized graphically here [Fig – 4].

Fig. 4 Brain Cell Tumour Size Mean Deviation Analysis

The incorrect detection of the size of the brain cell tumours can be highly inappropriate for further analysis. The size of the tumour cell is highly crucial for analysis on growth and pattern measures, which is again crucial for automation of the disease detection and predictions. Hence, nearly 100% accuracy is the most desirable factor during these detection processes. Hence, in the context, the improvements of detection accuracy are the demand of the current research trends.

Further, in the next section of this work, the survey conclusion is presented.

IX. SURVEY CONCLUSION

Henceforth, with the detailed analysis of the parallel research outcomes, in this section of the study, the final observations for brain tumour detection and prediction of the connected diseases are stated. In the initial phase of the research the outcome for the research is expected to demonstrate of novel pre-processing technique for MR Image normalization using a novel multi-lateral filtering technique, followed by justifying the applicability of Watershed method on MR Images for segmentation, demonstrating a improved watershed method for Brain Tumour Detection, detection of the Size of the tumours using diametric analysis, finally based on fuzzy rules, detection of the nature of the tumours for severity analysis. In the second phase of the research, study of MR Image types and comparison of the features must be carried out, follow by realizing the applicability of EM-GM method on MR Images for detection of diseases and finally detection of the location referenced to the skull interior must be showcased. Finally, in the final phase of the research, analysis of brain tumour-based disease detection for the following diseases, followed by mapping of tumour properties for analysis of possible diseases and finally demonstration of proposed framework results in disease prediction must be furnished.

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